

*Innovating for a low-carbon
and sustainable world*

Exploring CCUS: Chemical Looping Combustion as a Step Towards a Carbon-Free Energy

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AGENDA

- IFPEN Presentation
- Context of CCUS
 - What's CCUS and why
 - Deployment
- CCUS step by step from Capture to storage or utilization
 - Principles and examples of solutions
- Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC)
 - CHEERS, Oxy3C
- Conclusion

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IFPEN AT A GLANCE

Public sector
R&I institution

Training center

~ 500 graduates per year
> 50 nationalities

Industrial Group

~ 4000 collaborators
IFPEN + subsidiaries

INTERNATIONAL SCOPE in the field of
ENERGY, MOBILITY and THE ENVIRONMENT

1,543 employees

incl. **1,087** R&I engineers & technicians

€122 M Budget allocation in 2024

€154 M Own resources in 2024

From Oil and Gas legacy to Green technologies

Research & Innovation activities

Green technologies

Responsible & profitable Oil & Gas

FROM FUNDAMENTAL RESEARCH TO INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT

- R&I work on a variety of scales
 - Experimental setups from lab scale to pre-industrial pilot
 - Advanced digital tools: modeling and high-performance computing (HPC)
- In collaboration with academic and industrial partners

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WHAT IS CARBON CAPTURE UTILIZATION AND STORAGE (CCUS)?

WAY OF DECARBONATION

OUR SOLUTIONS ACROSS THE ENTIRE CCUS CHAIN

IFPEN GROUP PRESENT AT EACH STEP OF THE CHAIN

GLOBAL CONTEXT

Estimated CCS Needs: 350-1200 Gt (GIEC, 2020-2100)

Storing CO₂ underground to:

- ✓ **Massively reduce residual CO₂ emissions from industries**
 - ✓ Decarbonize « hard-to-abate sectors » (Energy, Industry – steel, ciment, chemistry...)
- ✓ **Removing CO₂ from the atmosphere (so-called negative emissions scenarios)**
 - ✓ Biomass Energy Carbon Capture and storage (BECCS)
 - ✓ Direct capture of CO₂ from the atmosphere (DACCS)

CCUS: a key technology to achieve carbon neutrality

CCS & CCU (EUROPE)

A LEGISLATIVE AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK IN PROGRESS

The Green Deal (2019) : aims for the EU to be carbon neutral by 2050

The Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). Expected to come into force in 2026.

The CO2 Geological Storage Directive (CCS Directive) provides a regulatory framework for CCS.

The European Climate Law (2021): legally binding climate neutrality target 2050

The Renewable Energy Directive encourages the deployment of CCU-based fuels to replace fossil fuels

Net-Zero Industry Act (2023) : offers CO2 storage capacities of:
50 Mt/year by 2030 (mandatory)
280 Mt/year by 2040
450 Mt/year by 2050

The Fit for 55 Package (2021): targets a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030

ReFuelEU aviation : enable the aviation sector to reduce its carbon footprint and create a level playing field for sustainable air transport in the EU.

EU ETS: the EU's central tool for reducing GHG emissions. No need for quotas if CO2 is captured and stored over the long term.

FuelEU Maritime: Encouraging the use of low-carbon renewable fuels and clean energy technologies for ships.

European legislations on Capture, Storage and Utilization (fuel mostly)

Only regional, no global legislations

CO₂ CAPTURE, UTILISATION AND STORAGE

FROM CONCEPT TO INDUSTRIAL REALITY

Leading projects in Europe :

Norway (Longship / Northern Lights), **the Netherlands** (Porthos / Aramis), **Denmark** (Greensand, Kalundborg), the **UK** (HyNet / Humber / Drax BECCS), and **Italy** (Ravenna).

What About France?

There is growing ambition and political will (ratification of the **London Protocol**), but **no large-scale industrial project** is operational yet.

51 Mt CO₂
captured and stored/year

628

large-scale projects

- 49 in operation
- 32 under construction
- 144 in advanced development stage
- 135 under assessment

for a capacity of
416 Mt CO₂/year

Even if all projects are successful, under the needs of NZE in 2030 (1GT/year)

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CAPTURE

POST-COMBUSTION

Decarbonizing effluents at the end of processes (Source Point)

Power generation, cement plants, steel industries, biogas

OXY-COMBUSTION

Combustion with pure oxygen to produce energy and recover pure CO₂

Energy production

PRE-COMBUSTION

Carbon is removed by steam reforming combining thermal reforming and partial oxidation, then CO is oxidized into CO₂ and H₂ is produced

Electricity and carbon-free hydrogen production (« blue H₂ »)

Capture

- DMX™ process
- Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC) process
- Breakthrough processes: process intensification, eco-efficient solvents, Direct Air Capture
- Design of integrated solutions

FLUE GAS POST-COMBUSTION CAPTURE: SECOND-GENERATION DMX™ PROCESS

Flue Gas CO₂ capture - DMX™ Process

In figures:
 ~2.5 GJ/tCO₂ depending on the application
 This is typically around 10% loss of efficiency on a thermal power plant

The advantages of the DMX process vs. 1st generation
 Energy consumption reduced by 30%
 Solvent more stable in temperature and oxidation
 Very pure and high-pressure CO₂

CHEMICAL LOOP COMBUSTION: WORKING PRINCIPLE

Use of a metal oxide to provide oxygen

Advantage: low energy penalty because oxycombustion without distilling the air to produce O_2 (ASU)

CO₂ CAPTURE AT IFPEN

CO₂ capture to treat Blast Furnace gas of ArcelorMittal steel plant

The timeline shows the progression of CO₂ capture technology at IFPEN:

- 2008:** Laboratory
- 2015:** Pilot
- 2020:** Industrial pilot

The industrial pilot unit is a tall, multi-story metal structure illuminated at night, with a capacity of **0.5 tCO₂/h**. It is part of the **3D DMX DEMONSTRATION DUNKIRK** project.

Logos at the bottom include: ifP Energies nouvelles, Axens (Powering integrated solutions), ArcelorMittal, and TotalEnergies.

« Curative technology » adaptable on existing industry

CO₂ capture with CLC (Chemical Looping Combustion) from industrial processes

The world's largest demonstration unit for CLC is a tall, blue metal structure, with a capacity of **(3 MWth)**. It is the result of **15 years of R&D** by the **CLCHEERS** project (中歐污染物减排技术研究).

Logos at the bottom include: ifP Energies nouvelles, Axens, ArcelorMittal, and TotalEnergies.

2023 : operation of the industrial pilot

« Avoiding technology », more dedicated to future industry

CO₂ TRANSPORT AND PURIFICATION

- One country, one CO₂ Hub
 - Topography, on shore or offshore storage, etc...
 - Hub and ways of transport
 - Pipelines
 - Boats
 - Trucks/train
- Purity and safety
 - Leaks : CO₂ odorless → Additives?
 - Different processes of capture → many impurities
 - Reactions, corrosion issues, etc...
 - Specifications for transport and storage
 - Norway : almost food grade specification → purifications needed

STORAGE

- Global storage capacity estimated to be well above the required requirement
 - Required Need :
 - 220 Gt (IEA, 2020 over the period 2020-2050)
 - 350-1200 Gt (GIEC, 2020-2100)
 - Theoretical estimation :
 - 8000-50 000 Gt (IEA, 2020)
 - > 28 000 Gt (ICIS, 2019)
 - EU ~ 507 Gt > 100 years of 2019 emissions

- Two main types of storage in porous rocks
 - Depleted reservoirs
 - Well known → Best 1st candidats
 - Deep Saline aquifers
 - Very promising
 - But need for advanced characterizations
Capacities, Caprock impermeability

Sustainability 2025, 17(7), 2904

Figure 2 : Estimation des ressources de stockage géologique de CO₂, dans le monde (en GtCO₂e) – Source : Global CCS Institute (2019).

CO₂ UTILIZATION

Current

Near

Futur

Green methanol to olefins (MTO), dimethyl ether and formic acid, polymers, proteins, ethanol, etc.

Large volumes (estimated ~430-640 Mtpy by 2040) but low / Gty requirement for the NZE scenario → **CCU and CCS complementary**

	UREA	Construction aggregates	CO ₂ Cured Concrete	e-kerosene	e-methanol
CO ₂ consumption	140 Mt/y	500-2000 Mt/y	40-70 Mt/y	50-150 Mt/y	130-280 Mt/y
Tech readiness	Controlled	Ready	Almost ready	Almost ready	Almost Ready
Limitations	Production of CO ₂	Price x2-x4	Price x1,5 Capex élevé	Price x2-x4 Green CO ₂ rarity and DAC	Price x2-x4 Green CO ₂ rarity and DAC
GES impact	-	≈Storage	≈Storage	Defossilization ressources optimization	Defossilization ressources optimization

The Oil and Gas Climate Initiative, White paper april 2024

● Economics

- CO₂ low energy → Products prices struggle to compete with fossil analogues prices
- CO₂ economics are strongly dependant on legislation and taxes
 - Highest confidence on E-fuels market since EU legislation
 - Less confidence on Chemicals since no legislation yet

LOW-CARBON FUELS

The 4 main pathways for 2030

The first industrial plants in France

BioTJet

nacre

Take Kair

THE FRENCH PROJECT TAKE KAIR

KEY ELEMENTS

The partners

Numbers

Budget ≈ 850 M€
 50 kty of e-fuel (e-KEROSENE, e-naphta, e-diesel)

Pays de Loire

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FOCUS ON CHEMICAL LOOPING COMBUSTION: FROM THE CONCEPT TO INDUSTRIAL SCALE

Cold mock-ups by tech blocks
FR, loop-seals, L-valve, ...

- TGA
- Batch CLC unit

Cold mock-up with complete loop

3 MW_{th}
demonstration
unit

10 kW_{th} continuous CLC unit

Industrial CLC
50 – 500 MW_{th}

FOCUS ON CHEMICAL LOOPING COMBUSTION (CLC) OPERATING CONDITIONS

	Thermal power	Fuel Flowrate		Oxygen carrier circulation flowrate	OC inventory	Temperature	Pressure	CO ₂ captured
	MWth	t/h	t/jour	t/h	t	°C	barg	t/an
IFPEN Pilot plant 10 kWth	0.01	0.0003	0.0072	0.02	0.02	950-1000	0.1-1.5	145
CHEERS demonstration unit 3 MWth	3	0.5	12	50 - 150	30			10 000
Industrial unit 50 MWth	50	7	170	900	100			150 000
Industrial unit 500 MWth	500	58	1400	1000	1000			1 460 000

- Consortium of 9 EU and CN Members
- From EU: SINTEF Energy AS (EU coordinator) & SINTEF AS, TotalEnergies, IFP Energies Nouvelles (IFPEN), Bellona, and Silesian University
- From CN: Dongfang Boiler Group Co (DBC), Tsinghua University (THU), and Zhejiang University
- **2017 – 2023 Project - Horizon 2020 - Research and Innovation Programm**
- EU grant Agreement N° 764697
- Chinese MOST - Minister of Science and Technology - CN grant

Located in Deyang (China)

CHEERS Objective
Demonstration of CLC technology

- Semi-industrial level: 3 MW_{th}
- Petcoke & Lignite feedstock
- Ilmenite Oxygen Carrier
- EPC done by DBC in Deyang

- RX height : 35 m
- Solid inventory : 70 t
- Solid flowrate : 50 – 150 t/h
- T : 900 – 1000 °C

From TR 4 to TRL 7

Pilot Unit in Solaize (IFPEN) – 10 kW_{th}

Demonstration Unit – 3 MW_{th}

KPI 1 : CCE: Carbon Capture Efficiency [1]

Carbon capture efficiency specifies how much of the carbon introduced with the solid fuel is captured in gaseous form at the fuel reactor outlet

Molar flow

$$CCE \text{ or } \eta_{CC}(\%) = \frac{F_{CO_2}^{FR,out} + F_{CO}^{FR,out} + F_{HC}^{FR,out} - F_{CO_2}^{FR,in}}{F_{CO_2}^{FR,out} + F_{CO}^{FR,out} + F_{HC}^{FR,out} - F_{CO_2}^{FR,in} + F_{CO_2}^{AR,out}}$$

Gas analyser

$$\chi_{O_2}(\%) = \frac{0.21 - y_{O_2,AR} - y_{CO_2,AR}}{0.21 - y_{O_2,AR} - 0.21 * y_{CO_2,AR}}$$

KPI 2 : OD: Oxygen demand [1]

The total oxygen demand represents the amount of oxygen needed for complete combustion of unconverted products compared to the oxygen required to convert the fuel fed to CO₂ and H₂O.

$$\Omega_T(\%) = \frac{4 * F_{CH_4}^{FR,out} + F_{CO}^{FR,out} + F_{H_2}^{FR,out}}{\frac{1}{M_O} * \Omega_{SF} * m_{SF}}$$

The oxygen demand in the fuel reactor (Ω_{FR}) is defined as the oxygen needed for complete combustion of unconverted gaseous products compared to the oxygen required to burn the fuel converted in the fuel reactor

$$\Omega_{FR}(\%) = \frac{4 * F_{CH_4}^{FR,out} + F_{CO}^{FR,out} + F_{H_2}^{FR,out}}{\frac{1}{M_O} * \Omega_{SF} * m_{SF} - 2 * F_{CO_2}^{AR,out} - 2 * F_{C,elut}}$$

Results CLC lignite

FR temp (°C)	AR top temp (°C)	Fuel flowrate (t/hr)	MW	OC flowrate (t/hr)	CO ₂ AR outlet (%v)	CO ₂ FR outlet (%v)	Carbon capture efficiency (%)	Total Oxygen demand (%)
900	1010	1,1	5	145	2,5 - 3	96,5	90 - 95	2,5 - 3

Autothermal CLC reached (no lignite in AR)

Good Carbon Capture Efficiency (CCE) with lignite: good conversion of lignite char

Low oxygen demand

COMPARISON WITH OTHER TECHNOLOGIES

- 1 application case → Power generation 200 MWe
- Petcoke fuel
- Comparison of technologies :
 - Ref case : Circulating Fluidized Bed (CFB) without amine CO₂ capture
 - CFB with amine CO₂ capture
 - CLC
 - CFB oxycombustion (ASU + CFB)

KPI 1 : LCOE (levelized cost of electricity) €/MWe_h

KPI 2 : CAC (CO₂ avoided cost) €/t CO₂

from CHEERS project

$$LCOE \left[\frac{\text{€}}{MW_e h} \right] = \frac{\text{Annualised CAPEX} + \text{Annual OPEX} [\text{€}]}{\text{Annual electrical output} [MW_e h]}$$

$$CAC \left[\frac{\text{€}}{tCO_2, \text{avoided}} \right] = \frac{LCOE_{CCS} - LCOE_{ref}}{e_{ref} - e_{CCS}}$$

PERSPECTIVES FOR CHEMICAL LOOPING COMBUSTION

➔ Biomass to Energy

➔ Waste to Energy

PERSPECTIVES FOR CHEMICAL LOOPING COMBUSTION

- An illustration of WtE CLC
 - A European project dedicated to CLC of SRF (solid recovered fuel)

LOUISE

Prepare for pre-commercial demonstration of Chemical Looping Combustion (CLC) of solid waste-derived fuels

10/2021 – 12/2024

from LOUISE project

ifp Energies nouvelles

SPLEEN program for industrial decarbonisation

Budget

• 70 M€ of public funding

Projects

• 10 already under way, 30+ expected

Training of high level early stage researchers

• 120+ PhD thesis, 1400 months post-doc

Partnership

• 40 + partners: **CNRS, IFPEN, CEA, INRAE, BRGM, INERIS**, Universities, Grandes écoles
• 70+ labs involved, located in France

- Positioning within the French national acceleration strategy France 2030 « industry decarbonisation »
- Propose a technological offering and breakthrough solutions that will contribute to France's climate commitments by 2050
- Research program aimed at transforming industrial processes to make them less GHG-emitting (technologies in the TRL 1-4 range)

21 RESEARCH PROJECTS

AXIS 1

New prediction tools and monitoring

DCARBO

Real-time monitoring

LCA SPLEEN

Minimising the environmental impact of decarbonisation

ACT-4IE

Industrial and regional ecology

SPECULAR

Multi-scale evaluation

AXIS 2

Integration of low carbon energy vectors, efficiency

SHIP4D

Solar heat for decarbonisation

AMYABLE

Combustion mechanisms

FROZEN

Flexible burners

REHEAT

Vapor-compression heat pump

ATHENA

Cold production system using thermal energy

REVCO2

Supercritical CO₂ Brayton cycle

AXIS 3

Decarbonization of the processes, intensification

ECOCEM

Catalysts and efficient processes

PLASMA-N-ACT

Ammonia electrosynthesis

IMOSYCCA

Modular CO₂ capture systems

CATALPA

Low-temperature and electrified CO₂ capture

OXY3C

CO₂ capture by oxycombustion

NEWIRON

Production of sustainable steel

AXIS 4

CO₂ storage and valorization

POWER CO₂

Conversion of CO₂: fuels and chemical synthons

COCINNELLE

Production of carbonate by biomineralisation

CARBIOCEM

Carbonating cement through biomineralisation

CARBONARA

Production of polycarbonates

SESAME

Sociotechnical trajectory for onshore geological storage of CO₂

OXY3C PROJECT (PEPR SPLEEN)

- Oxy3C = Carbon Captur by eco-efficient OXYCombustion processes
- Bring together an oxy-combustion community focusing on two areas : oxy-flames and CLC
- Biofuels as raw material for heat production (biogas for oxy-flames and biomass for CLC)

→ Oxyflames : development of new burners adapted to oxy-combustion

→ CLC : reaction pathways involved in biomass chemical looping combustion

Experimentation
Modeling
Kinetics

8 French partners

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CONCLUSION

- The large-scale deployment of CCS and CCU is essential to achieve our climate goals by 2050
- Several barriers
 - Clarify the economic, regulatory, and financial frameworks
 - Industry, investors, and public stakeholders need a predictable and consistent market with long-term visibility
 - Developing business models to compensate imbalance between heavy investments now vs long term benefits (avoiding emission penalties)
 - Reducing costs across the entire CCS and CCU value chain
- Several levers
 - Clarifying financial responsibility for CO₂ across the entire chain, by establishing a robust framework for the certification of avoided or removed emissions
 - Securing early investments through public subsidiaries, tax credits, or guaranteed price mechanisms
- For IFPEN, CCUS should be seen as a major industrial opportunity
 - To strength our territories in future-oriented sectors
 - To create jobs and anchor technological solutions
- CLC is a proven technology to produce energy while capturing CO₂ emissions
 - Wide variety of acceptable fuels (from fossil to waste/biomass fuels)
 - A dynamic international community with projects led by countries or continents

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3MW_{TH} CLC DEMONSTRATION UNIT

